

Local Government in Switzerland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Switzerland: An Introduction

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In Switzerland, all three tiers of government, namely the Confederation, the cantons (states) and the communes (municipalities), have the right to levy taxes to the extent that the Federal Constitution does not limit these public bodies (Article 3 of the Constitution). While the two upper tiers enjoy a full sovereignty, the communes only have a derived sovereignty as their right to levy taxes can be limited by the cantons.

The fiscal autonomy of the communes is rooted in the Swiss federal system. Although one sees a trend towards more centralization of competencies, the principle of subsidiarity is still a pillar of the system: tasks that can be done at a lower political level should be done at a lower level, closer to the people concerned by them. Thus, Swiss communes are not in charge of minor duties only (waste removal) but are also competent for tasks of higher importance such as education, social care, etc. Consequently, the communes levy approximately 20 per cent of the total tax revenue of the three administrative tiers²³.

In the case of Switzerland, where budgets are highly decentralized, the equalization of resources and the equalization of charges are two tools that help mitigate imbalances among public bodies. These imbalances can be of different natures. For example, the amount of tax revenue can be very unbalanced (i.e. equalization of resources) and the burden of financing public services can be highly unevenly distributed between urban and rural communes (i.e. equalization of charges).

In 2008, Switzerland introduced a fiscal equalization system between the Confederation and the cantons accompanied by an inter-cantonal distribution (subnational level). The Federal Act on fiscal equalization and expenditures compensation entered into force in 2003 and was revised in 2019. Practically, the financial flows are multiple, horizontal and vertical, and the overall system is quite complex. A chart resuming the system is available on the website of the Swiss Federal Department of Finance:²⁴

²³ In 2014, tax revenues (3 tiers) totaled CHF 131 billion: Confederation: CHF 60,6 billion; cantons: CHF 43,5 billion; communes: CHF 26,8.

²⁴ '2021 fiscal equalization payments in CHF mn' (*Federal Department of Finance*)

<<https://www.efd.admin.ch/efd/en/home/themen/finanzpolitik/national-fiscal-equalization/fb-nationaler-finanzausgleich/grafik-nfa.html>> last accessed 15 February 2020.

Figure 1: Fiscal equalization system between the Swiss Confederation and the cantons.

At the local level, similar mechanisms are in place within the cantons. As each canton developed its own specific intercommunal equalization system, carrying out a comprehensive survey of the different schemes is a challenging endeavor. In 2013, the think tank Avenir Suisse published an interesting comparative monitoring of all the 26 intercommunal systems.²⁵ The author underlined that the majority of the intercommunal equalization systems were often unnecessarily complicated, encouraged spending behaviors and thus maintained inefficient municipal structures.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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²⁵ Lukas Rühli, *Monitoring des Cantons 5: Le Labyrinthe de la péréquation financière* (Avenir Suisse 2013) 21.

Website of the Swiss Conference of the Cantonal Governments, <<https://kdk.ch/fr/>>

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